

On a causal force constraint mechanism for approximate position tracking wave energy control strategies

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Abstract—This paper addresses the design of a causal force constraint mechanism (FCM), a crucial complement for the implementation of non-optimisation-based (non-OB) control algorithms for wave energy converters (WEC). The proposed FCM keeps the power take-off (PTO) control effort within specific physical thresholds, which has significant implications for maintaining the integrity of the associated WEC and power PTO components.

The proposal presented in this paper requires a position tracking control structure and, thus, a simple procedure to obtain a position reference using the non-OB controllers, Simple & Effective and LiteCon+, is presented. Then, FCM operates by conditioning the position reference as the control effort approaches a physical threshold. To show the efficacy of the proposal, results are obtained by evaluating the constraint method on a modified closed-loop version of LiTe-Con+. The results show that, with a small increase in complexity, the PTO control force is effectively and robustly kept within the constraints.

Index Terms—Causal control, force constraints, wave energy.

I. INTRODUCTION

WAVE energy control strategies may be broadly divided into two categories. The first category includes optimization-based (OB) control strategies, which provide constrained energy-maximizing solutions by resorting to numerical routines [1]. In contrast, the second category comprises non-optimization-based (non-OB) control strategies, which do not rely on numerical routines and provide (suboptimal) real-time implementable solutions. Although non-OB strategies represent an appealing alternative to implementing real-time control of wave energy converters (WECs),

to the best of the authors' knowledge, none of the existing non-OB strategies can handle force (alternatively, torque) constraints to limit the operational space of the control action [2].

Hence, this paper addresses the design of a simple force constraint mechanism (FCM), which is based on a reference conditioning principle [3] [4]. The rationale behind using reference conditioning is simple: A large, or rapidly varying, reference results in a large control effort required to track such a reference. Hence, as the control force approaches a design threshold, the reference is penalised (conditioned) to prevent surpassing the force constraint. Naturally, to implement FCM, a reference tracking control structure is required and, in this paper, to guarantee satisfaction for both position and force constraints, a position reference is used.

To robustly achieve satisfaction of force constraints, two modulation mechanisms are simultaneously employed: A linear feedback correction term that continuously penalises the reference and acts as a soft constraint modulation method, and a sliding-mode (SM) reference conditioning (SMRC) strategy [3] [4], that keeps the control force on a sliding surface, and acts as a hard constraint modulation method. Importantly, the combination of the soft and hard modulation methods prevents the control effort from exceeding the specified constraint while providing the designer with design flexibility. Also, it is worth noting that SMRC is only operative when the control force approaches the constraint, but does not affect nominal operation conditions when the control effort is far from the constraint limits.

In this work, how to obtain the required position reference by using two non-OB controllers for WECs: The 'Simple and Effective' (S&E) control [5] [6], and a modified closed-loop version of LiTe-Con+ [7] [8], is also presented. Although both S&E and LiteCon+ are capable of handling soft position constraints, as outlined in their original proposals, they do not possess mechanisms for handling force constraints [2]. Hence, this paper illustrates how it is possible to use both S&E and LiteCon+ as reference generators, and combine them with the FCM presented in this paper, to design a causal closed-loop control algorithm for WECs that satisfies both position and force constraints.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. In Section II, the position tracking structure required for the implementation of FCM is presented. In Section III, the causal soft and hard force constraint meth-

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ods are presented and separately analysed. Section IV presents in-silico evaluations, conducted to assess the performance of the proposed method. Finally, the main conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. TRACKING CONTROL FOR WECs

In this Section, the WEC control strategy, based on a position tracking structure, is presented. To that end, first, the employed WEC model is presented in Subsection II-A. Then, Subsection II-B presents the position tracking control strategy.

A. Hydrodynamic WEC modelling fundamentals

Applying Newton's second law, together with linear hydrodynamic assumptions [9], the dynamics of a one-degree-of-freedom WEC are given by:

$$\Sigma_w : \begin{cases} \dot{v} = \mathcal{M}(-\mathbf{h}\mathbf{q} - k_x x + f_e + f_u), & (1a) \\ \dot{x} = v, & (1b) \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{g}\mathbf{v}, & (1c) \\ y = v, & (1d) \end{cases}$$

where x is displacement, v is velocity, $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r}$ are the radiation states, with the associated radiation system triple $(\mathbf{F}, \mathbf{g}, \mathbf{h})$ strictly passive [10], \mathcal{M}^{-1} is the total WEC mass, and f_e is the wave excitation force, modelled as an external bounded disturbance with zero mean. Let $\mathbf{x}^\top = [z, v, \mathbf{q}]^\top$, and rewrite (1) as:

$$\Sigma_w : \begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}(f_e + f_u), & (2a) \\ y = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}. & (2b) \end{cases}$$

B. Position tracking architecture

The position tracking (PT) control structure used in this paper is presented in Figure 1. In essence, the PT structure requires a position reference, which is provided by an outer control loop (detailed in the following Subsection II-B), and a tracking structure (inner loop) capable of robustly tracking the provided position reference. In the following, the outer and inner loops are presented.

Figure 1. Illustrative diagram of PT control loop for WECs.

1) *Outer loop - Position reference generation based on non-OB controllers:* Typically, the WEC control problem is associated with extremising a cost function over an interval $T \in \mathbb{R}_+$, subject to system constraints [11] as:

$$\begin{aligned} f_u &= \arg \max_{f_u} \{ \mathcal{J}_T(f_u) \}, \\ \text{s.t.} & \\ & \text{System dynamics,} \\ & \text{Physical constraints,} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where f_u is designed to extremise the cost function $\mathcal{J}_T(f_u)$. In this paper, it is assumed that $\mathcal{J}_T(f_u)$ is defined as the integral of converted mechanical power, and the non-OB solutions for problem (3) obtained from S&E and LiteCon+, that only satisfy position constraints, are used. Then, from the suboptimal solution to problem (3), a position reference, $z^*(t)$, is used as input for the tracking controller, as detailed in Subsection II-B2.

The procedure to use the S&E and LiTe-Con+ controllers as reference generators is as follows. Essentially, by using a measured wave excitation force, the corresponding controllers are designed and applied to *virtual* WEC models. Then, the desired variables from the *virtual* system response are obtained. Specifically, for S&E and LiteCon+, the required steps are as follows:

(a) LiTe-Con+ (See Figure 2.a):

- 1) Using an estimate of the wave excitation force, f_e , compute the required control force;
- 2) Apply the control force to the virtual WEC model;
- 3) Obtain the required variables, i.e., position, velocity, or control force, as applicable.

(b) S&E (See Figure 2.b):

- 1) Using an estimate of the wave excitation force, f_e , compute the velocity reference;
- 2) By using a virtual plant model, design the required IMC controller;
- 3) Close the loop and control the virtual WEC model;
- 4) Obtain the required variables, i.e., position, velocity, or control force as applicable.

Figure 2. Illustration of the method to obtain a position reference using (a) Lite-Con, and (b) S&E.

2) *Inner loop - Position tracking control:* In this paper, an internal model-based tracking control (IMC) is employed for the low-level control loop. In the scheme from Figure 1, the main objective of IMC is to robustly track the position reference, even in the presence of WEC model uncertainty. IMC exploits the concept that, for stable processes, feedback is only necessary in the presence of model uncertainty. Following the design guidelines presented in [6], IMC may be designed using the Youla-Kučera parametrisation, which provides the family of all stabilising controllers for system (1), parametrised by a proper rational stable transfer function $Q(s)$. Hence, let $G_0(s) = \mathbf{C}(s\mathbb{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B}$, be the Laplace transfer function of the nominal system

(2). Then, the family of all stabilising controllers $K(s)$, for $G_0(s)$, is given by:

$$C(s) = \frac{Q(s)}{1 - Q(s)G_0(s)}, \quad (4)$$

where $Q(s)$ is

$$Q(s) = \tilde{Q}(s)G_0^{-1}(s), \quad (5)$$

and $\tilde{Q}(s)$ a user-defined transfer function, designed considering that the stability of $Q(s)$ is necessary and sufficient to guarantee stability of the associated closed loop in Figure 1. Naturally, the selection of $Q(s)$ (equivalently, of $\tilde{Q}(s)$) is not unique. The approach used, in this paper, is to design $\tilde{Q}(s)$ as:

$$\tilde{Q}(s) = \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{s}{\omega_c})^{n_c}}, \quad (6)$$

where ω_c defines a cut-off frequency, and n_c is the filter order. The user-defined variables, ω_c and n_c , are designed considering the trade-off between tracking performance and noise attenuation.

III. FORCE CONSTRAINT MECHANISM VIA REFERENCE CONDITIONING

Using the control scheme in Figure 1, the position constraints are inherently satisfied, because the IMC reference, z^* , obtained via causal control, inherently considers position constraints. However, tracking z^* may require large PTO control forces and the control action f_u may violate the constraint:

$$|f_u(t)| \leq f_{max}. \quad (7)$$

Importantly, designing a *causal* force constraint mechanism for non-OB controllers has not been addressed in the literature. Hence, in this section, a hard constraint mechanism that satisfies (7) $\forall t$, for the PT structure in Figure 1, is presented. The method combines a soft constraint loop, presented in Section III-A, and a hard constraint loop, based on SM, formalised in Section III-B.

Figure 3. Force constraint method applied to PT control for WECs.

A. Soft force constraint loop

By resorting to continuous-time penalisation of the position reference, the soft FCM can reduce the operational space of the control force.

The soft constraint loop operates by comparing the output of the controller, f_u , with the output of a continuous and smooth saturation map $\mathcal{S} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Let $\mathcal{S}(\cdot)$ be defined as:

$$\mathcal{S}(f_u) = 2f_M \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{1 + e^{-2f_u/f_M}} \right). \quad (8)$$

An example of (8) with $f_M = 1$ is presented in Figure 4. The saturation map provides a control force reference that does not violate the predefined constraints. Hence, define $e_f = \mathcal{S}(f_u) - f_u$ as an error signal. Using e_f , an auxiliary control, \mathcal{C}_{sc} , is included to penalise the position reference by using a control signal w_s , as presented in the \mathcal{S}_c block in Figure 3. It is important to note that $e_f = 0$ is achieved only with the trivial solution, $f_u = 0$, since $f_u - \mathcal{S}(f_u) = 0$ only for $f_u = 0$. Thus, control \mathcal{C}_{sc} is included to reduce f_u , but not to track $e_f = 0$ robustly. In this paper, \mathcal{S}_c is designed using a nonlinear gain, as presented in the results Section IV.

Figure 4. Normalised saturation map using (8) with $f_M = 1$.

B. Hard SM-based force constraint loop

SMRC is a hard constraint method that complements the soft FCM from Subsection III-A. In opposition to classic SM control, SMRC does not operate continuously and is only active in a region defined by the constraints. Specifically, to satisfy constraint (7), when the control action, f_u , reaches a sliding manifold, SMRC reduces (penalises) the IMC reference, z^* , limiting the operational space of the control force.

SMRC is composed of three subsystems (see Figure 3): (i) A user-defined switching function $\sigma(\cdot)$, (ii) a commutation block where a discontinuous action is implemented, and (iii) a low-pass filter (LPF), which provides a smooth output of the SMRC, w_s . Additionally, assume that the control force may be saturated, and define the saturated control force \hat{f}_u as:

$$\hat{f}_u = \begin{cases} f_{max} & \text{if } f_u > f_{max}, \\ f_u & \text{if } -f_{max} < f_u < f_{max}, \\ f_{min} & \text{if } f_u < -f_{max}. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The main objective of SMRC is to limit the control force, f_u , between two surfaces, \bar{S} and \underline{S} , defined by

the switching function $\sigma(\cdot)$, and designed to ensure constraint (7). Formally, \bar{S} and \underline{S} are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{S} &= \{x_c \in \mathcal{X}_c : \sigma |_{\dot{f}_u=f_{max}} = 0\}, \\ \underline{S} &= \{x_c \in \mathcal{X}_c : \sigma |_{\dot{f}_u=-f_{max}} = 0\}.\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

where $x_c \in \mathcal{X}_c \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is the IMC controller state. By keeping the control variables between the surfaces defined by \bar{S} and \underline{S} , the controller operational space is limited to satisfy constraint (7). To force $\sigma = 0$, when the control force, f_u , approaches the constraint limits, the discontinuous signal, w ,

$$w = \begin{cases} w^+ & \text{if } \sigma < 0 \\ w^- & \text{if } \sigma > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \sigma = 0 \end{cases}\quad (11)$$

is implemented in the commutation block. An illustrative scheme of the SMRC operation is presented in Figure 5. Note that, if x_c is between \bar{S} , \underline{S} , then

Figure 5. Graphical interpretation of the SMRC operation.

$\sigma = 0$, $w = 0$, and the reference is not modified (SMRC is not active). However, when x_c reaches \bar{S} , or \underline{S} , σ becomes nonzero, and the control force is driven to $\sigma = 0$ via w , preventing $f_u = C_c x_c$ from exceeding the specified constraints. To design the SMRC, the following conditions are required:

- (C1) **Transversality condition** [12]. The switching function σ is of unitary relative degree with respect to the discontinuous action ($\dot{\sigma}$ must be an explicit function of w),
- (C2) **Gain condition** [12]. The amplitudes w^+ , w^- , satisfy:

$$\begin{aligned}0 &< \underline{w}_{eq} < w^+ \\ w^- &< \bar{w}_{eq} < 0\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

where \underline{w}_{eq} and \bar{w}_{eq} are *equivalent* continuous actions.

While w^+ , w^- , may be empirically selected to satisfy (C2), the relative degree condition, (C1), typically requires analysis of the control variables in the considered application.

IV. FORCE CONSTRAINT TUNING AND NUMERICAL EVALUATION

In the following, results using the force constraint mechanism are presented. First, Subsection IV-A presents the simulation parameters, and Subsections IV-B and IV-C present the parameters used to tune the soft and hard FCMs. Finally, results in the time domain are presented in Subsection IV-C.

A. WEC and simulation parameters

Consider a one-degree-of-freedom point-absorber-like WEC with dynamics (1) with $\mathcal{M} = 6.8 \times 10^{-6}$, $k_x = 5.57 \times 10^5$, and \mathbf{F} , \mathbf{g} , and \mathbf{h} given by:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} -7 & -24 & -47 & -57 & -43 & -18 & -3.4 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13a)$$

$$\mathbf{g} = [1.46 \cdot 10^5 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^\top, \quad (13b)$$

$$\mathbf{h} = [0.21 \ 1.1 \ 3.8 \ 4.6 \ 3 \ 0.64 \ 0.014] \cdot 10^{-5}. \quad (13c)$$

Also, to generate a realistic wave profile, $f_e(t)$ is generated using the Bretschneider spectrum, considering a peak period $T_p = 8s$, and significant wave height $H_s = 1.2m$. Additionally, it is considered that the WEC under study must satisfy the constraints given by:

$$|f_u| \leq f_M = 0.8 \cdot 10^6 N, \quad (14)$$

$$|z| \leq z_M = 2m. \quad (15)$$

B. Design of the soft constraint loop

The soft constraint FCM loop is tuned using (8), considering force constraint (14), and designing C_{sc} as:

$$C_{sc} : \begin{cases} u = 10^{-4} |e_f|^{1/2} \text{sign}(e_f), \\ \dot{w}_s = 10(u - w_s), \end{cases}\quad (16a)$$

$$(16b)$$

which is, essentially, a non-linear filtered proportional-like control which only penalises, smoothly, the position reference z^* .

C. Design of the hard constraint loop

In this section, the SMRC operational conditions, (C1) and (C2), detailed in Subsection III-A, are used in the SMRC design for the WEC system detailed in Subsection IV-B. To that end, $\sigma(\cdot)$, and the LPF are designed considering PT closed-loop control (see Figure 3).

First, to verify (C1), the relative degree of f_u , with respect to w_h , is evaluated. To that end, the IMC controller, designed in Section II-B, is rewritten in state-space form as:

$$C(s) : \begin{cases} \dot{x}_c = A_c x_c + B_c e_c \\ f_u = C_c x_c, \end{cases}\quad (17)$$

where $x_c \in \mathcal{X}_c \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is the controller state, $A_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times n_c}$ is the dynamic matrix, $B_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times 1}$ is the input matrix, and $C_c \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n_c}$ is the output matrix. Additionally, let:

$$e_c = z^* + w_s + w_h - z, \quad (18)$$

be the conditioned error, with w_h being the SMRC output, provided by a first-order LPF:

$$LPF : \{\dot{w}_h = 0.7(w - w_h)\}, \quad (19)$$

with w being the output of the discontinuous block in (11). In this paper, the IMC control is designed

such that f_u is of relative degree 1 with respect to e_c . Hence, to satisfy (C1), considering that e_c is of relative degree one with respect to w (due to (19)), $\sigma(\cdot)$ must be a function of the 1st-time derivative of f_u . Thus, the commutation function is designed as:

$$\sigma = \hat{f}_u - f_u - k_\alpha f_u^{(1)}, \quad (20)$$

with $k_\alpha = 10^{-3}$. Note that (20) determines the allowed region:

$$\mathcal{R} = \{x_c \in \mathcal{X}_c : \sigma = 0\}. \quad (21)$$

Thus, if $|f_u + k_\alpha f_u^{(1)}|$ tends to exceed f_M , then $w \neq 0$, and (11) and (20) force $|f_u + \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\rho} k_\alpha f_u^{(\alpha)}|$ to remain in \mathcal{R} , modifying the reference z^* . In practice, z^* is conditioned before f_u reaches f_M , since the derivative $|k_\alpha f_u^{(\alpha)}|$ introduces conservatism in the design of $\sigma(\cdot)$, in (20).

It is important to consider that the designed SMRC-based force constraint mechanism is not active when $|f_u + k_\alpha f_u^{(1)}| < f_M$. Subsequently, the SMRC method does not alter $z^*(t)$ in \mathcal{R} . With respect to design condition (C2), the value $w^+ = -w^-$, is selected considering the infinity norm of the conditioned reference, i.e., $w^+ = w^- = \|z^*\|_\infty = 2$, given the position constraint established for the system under study. If required, however, w^+ , and w^- , may be empirically tuned by resorting to numerical evaluation.

D. Numerical evaluation in the time domain

First, for simplicity sake, the results presented in this section are obtained using only LiteCon+ with the scheme from Figure 2.a, since results with the S&E controller are equivalent. Then, the performance of the soft constraint mechanism is evaluated in the time domain. In Figure 6, the PTO force used for the virtual WEC is compared with the conditioned PTO force when only the soft constraint method is used. Essentially, the soft constraint mechanism penalises the position reference (Figure 7.a), and reduces the PTO control action. Due to the selection of the saturation map \mathcal{S} , the soft correction term w_s increases with e_f , as observed in Figures 6.b and 6.c.

In addition, the position and velocity responses are presented in Figure 7. Here, it is noted that the LiteCon+ position reference inherently satisfies the position constraint (in Figure 7.a). However, it can also be appreciated that, to reduce the control effort, the conditioned position reference is penalised with w_s , resulting in a position profile with less amplitude.

While the soft constraint loop penalises the position reference, it is not sufficiently robust to keep the control force within constraint (14). Hence, including the SMRC-based hard constraint mechanism guarantees robust satisfaction of the force constraints, as can be appreciated in Figure 8.

Although the soft constraint method does not satisfy constraint (14) on its own, its presence reduces the action required for the hard constraint SMRC mechanism. That is, the gains $w^+ = -w^-$ can be reduced to a small value, reducing the chattering effect apparent in the control action in Figure 8. Also, note, in Figure 9, the

Figure 6. Time trace of the PTO control force using only the soft constraint loop. (a) Nominal and conditioned PTO control forces. (b) Error e_f .

Figure 7. Time trace of position and velocity. (a) Nominal and conditioned position. (b) Nominal and conditioned velocity.

difference with respect to the case presented in Figure 7. Specifically, when SMRC is included, it is noted that penalisation on the position reference is more severe, due to the combination of w_s and w_h , both of which are included and combined to satisfy constraint (14). This is also visualised in the amplitude of $w_s + w_h$, presented in Figure 8.c.

It is also interesting to note the effect of conditioning the position reference on the resultant velocity profile. Notably, conditioning the position reference results in velocity profiles with smaller amplitudes when compared to the nominal (reference) case, shown in Figures 7.b and 9.b. Hence, it is possible to confirm that the operational space of position and velocity has to be reduced to satisfy compliance with the force constraint. Naturally, this also indicates that, when force constraints are included, the absorbed power is reduced.

Furthermore, it is important to consider that the force constraint mechanism does not *anticipate* saturation of the control force, and when the constraint limit is reached, the design method does not preserve optimality of LiteCon+ in the sense stated in [7] [8]. Hence, in future research, the proposed constraint method could be tuned to optimise the performance with respect to power absorption.

Figure 8. Time trace of the PTO control force using the hard constraint loop. (a) Nominal and conditioned PTO control forces. (b) Error e_f .

Figure 9. Time trace of position and velocity. (a) Nominal and conditioned velocity. (b) Nominal and conditioned position.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a novel force constraint mechanism (FCM) for causal non-OB wave energy controllers is introduced. Remarkably, the only requirement for the use of FCM is that a closed-loop reference tracking structure is used. FCM operates by modulating the

control reference in order to prevent exceeding the constraint limits. To that end, two reference conditioning signals are used: The first is a soft constraint signal, based on a complementary control loop, and the second, implemented as a hard constraint signal, is obtained by using an SMRC technique.

The design of a robust force constraint method is essential for real-time implementation to protect the PTO and WEC from damage. Hence, the presented FCM addresses a fundamental aspect required for the implementation of closed-loop non-OB control for WECs. Additionally, the proposed structure could also be a fundamental tool for closed-loop OB controllers, since the accuracy and robustness of the proposed FCM are independent of the system dynamics. Overall, the methodology presented in this paper is broadly applicable to different tracking structures and could serve as an essential tool for real-time implementation of control algorithms for WECs. Hence, future work includes real-time testing and validation of FCMs in experimental tanks.

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